

The bearing of Dr. Meghnad Saha's researches on the problem of cosmic evolution†

Sir P. C. Ray

During the middle ages in Europe, all geographical books began with a map of the world with Jerusalem as the centre of the earth and consequently of the universe. Childish as such ideas may appear to us now, they illustrate a tendency in all ages running through the human mind – namely, to understand the position of man with respect to the phenomenal world, and to build a picture on the available knowledge. In all these attempts – whether they were made on the banks of the Nile, the Tigris or the Ganges, whether in classic Greece or medieval Rome, man was obsessed with a ridiculous idea of his own importance, and his ideas of geography and cosmogony were tainted with his own religious beliefs.

There is nothing to choose between these theories. In the light of modern knowledge, they are all equally puerile. Jerusalem or Mecca, Mount Olympus or the Himalayas can no more claim to be called the centre of the world than any Negro village in the interior of Africa.

The universe of facts is the result of century long studies by savants of all ages, and is truly an international achievement. It was preceded by a knowledge of the shape of the earth, which we owe to the Alexandrian savant Eratosthenes. We know that this earth of ours is only a tiny piece of pebble in the vast space. Its parent is the sun, from which it separated millions of years ago, as a tiny spark is thrown off from a mass of coal on fire. Life, vegetation, man – are the results of a process of cooling extending over millions of years.

A new celestial 'Geography' has succeeded the older fanciful geography of Ptolemy, and how the old ideas have been clean swept off will be manifest from one example. In ancient and medieval times, the curiosity of man to know the origin of the myriads of stars shining about us gave rise to many enjoyable stories, e.g., the stars are the souls of some departed heroes who, as reward for their meritorious deeds, have been allowed by the Gods to have a place in the firma-

ment.

But alas! at the touch of the Goddess of Science, all these stories have vanished like so many day-dreams! We now know that each one of these stars is a sun, some smaller but most larger than our own sun, each having its own family of planets, probably peopled with rational beings like ourselves, each with its own set of warring nations and intriguing politicians! By applying the same method by means of which a surveyor determines the distance and height of a far-off tower or hill, the astronomer can measure the distance separating us from these stars.

This trigonometric survey of the heavens, first begun by Bessel of Königsberg in 1839, is still being carried out according to well-laid-out plans in all the chief observatories of the world, on a basis of international co-operation. They tell us a really wonderful tale; they show, at the same time, how small is man, and yet how big is his intellect! Our nearest stellar neighbour, alpha-centauri, a first class star in the southern heavens, is twenty-five billions of miles distant from us. Even light, which in a second covers nearly 2 lakhs of miles, and takes only eight minutes to reach the earth from the sun, takes full four years and a half to reach us from our nearest stellar neighbour. Space is full of apparently an unlimited number of such island universes, I say "apparently", because Professor Einstein has recently cried halt to this idea of the limitless extent of the universe. He holds that the physical universe, though unbounded is not limitless – the total number of island-universes not exceeding 10^{21} which is of the order of thousand trillions.

In spite of the immensity of the universe, the same laws with which Newton unlocked the mystery of planetary motion are found to govern these distant worlds. Thousands of such worlds were discovered by that great explorer of heavens, – Herschel, but in none has the law of gravitation been found non-existent. This is an instance of the fundamental

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identity of physical phenomena.

The new heavens and the new cosmogony

The overthrow of older ideas left a blank in man's mind. But "Nature abhors a vacuum", and it was not long before Kant and Laplace hastened to fill up the gap by their famous Nebular Hypothesis. The influence of this hypothesis on the subsequent course of science can be illustrated by the following episode.

In ancient times, two clever Greeks, Daedalus and Icarus, father and son, are said to have built wings, and cruised through the sky. Daedalus kept himself near the earth, and successfully performed the journey. Icarus was more ambitious and wanted to reach the sun. But on close approach to the sun, the wax of his wings melted and he fell into the sea and was drowned,

In science, too, a theory which attempts too much, runs the risk of sharing Icarus's fate. But closer scrutiny will show that Icarus's failures are more valuable to mankind than Daedalus's triumphs. Daedalus confining himself to low heights, cannot see more than the man on the earth. Icarus, in this soaring cruise, comes across new sights and new phenomena, which is the net gain to man's store of knowledge, surviving his own fate. Many people would liken the nebular hypothesis to Icarus's journey, and would predict for it the same fate. But be that as it may, it was a sublime thought, attempting to bring within one compass the knowledge of the heavens brought to light with the aid of Galileo's telescope, Newton's law of gravitation, and Herschel's survey of the heavens. Within the last hundred years, it had many ups and downs, but has been, on the whole, able to retain its ground, and meet the demands arising out of new discoveries.

Laplace postulated a theory of stellar evolution, from a primordial nebular mass by a process of gradual contraction. The contraction is the result of mutual gravitational attraction of the nebular gas, attended by a spin of the whole mass round an axis. Laplace never saw the nebulae himself, and it is doubtful if he ever pictured to himself the various stages of his worlds in the making. The nebulae were first photographed by Lord Rosse with his giant telescope in 1840; after that thousands of them have been discovered by enterprising European and American observers, many of them showing the spin, the structure, and nuclei of condensation predicted by Laplace.

The study of the various stages of evolution of the stellar worlds remained unsolved till 1860. The stars are presumably quite as big as the sun, or much bigger, but such an immense distance separates them from us that even in the biggest telescopes they appear as mere specks of light. With the apparatus at our disposal before 1860, it was like attempting to scan the coloured lines on a child's marble with the naked eye from a distance of one mile.

Yet this seemingly impracticable step was rendered possible by the discovery of spectrum analysis by Kirchoff of Heidelberg in 1860. This method, it is well known, enables us to determine the constituents of any luminous mass by analysing the light emitted by it, under the influence of heat or electricity. Every element, when excited by the electrical spark, or placed in the flame or the electrical arc, emits light of a particular colour. If it is seen through a glass prism, the colour is decomposed into a number of lines, which is characteristic of that element. Every element has its own array of lines, which is as distinct from the set possessed by another element, as the finger print of one individual differs from that of another.

The solar light, when it is seen through a prism, gives the well-known colours of the rainbow. But closer scrutiny shows that this spectrum is crossed by a number of fine, dark lines. They were detected by Fraunhofer of Munich in 1814, and, for a long time, were a source of great puzzle to the scientists. Afterwards it so turned out that they were the hieroglyphics in which the sun-god has written out his own story.

The decipherment was accomplished by Kirchoff, the Champollion of the stellar worlds. He showed that many of the dark lines were identical in position with the lines of known elements; for example, the lines called by Fraunhofer D were the same as the yellow lines seen in a sodium flame. Kirchoff argued that this shows that sodium is present in the atmosphere of the sun.

"Once the ice was broken", began the race for the pole! Kirchoff himself identified iron, calcium, strontium, nickel, cobalt and about ten other elements in the atmosphere of the sun. The astronomers who followed him, notably Rowland of America, discovered no less than 20,000 lines, but of these only 6,000 have been identified.

Let us now pause for a while to consider the bearing of this discovery on the problems of stellar evolution. The earth is only a fragment of the sun, so the sun ought to show the

very same elements as the earth. The earth is composed of 92 elements, but in the sun we get only forty. To take one example, in the alkali group, we have lithium, sodium, potassium, rubidium, and caesium. In the sun, the lines of sodium are very prominent, lithium can be identified, and potassium is very feebly represented. But not the slightest trace of rubidium or caesium can be found.

This is not the whole discrepancy. The chief constituents of the crust of the earth are oxygen, silicon, iron, carbon, aluminium. In the sun, on the other hand, oxygen, silicon, carbon, aluminium are represented by rather faint lines. Iron, calcium, nickel are represented by numerous sets of strong lines. In other words, there seem to be no correspondence between the composition of the sun and that of the earth.

The sun is only one of the numberless stars, by no means distinguished above its fellows. There are other stars which, if they were brought to the same distance as the sun, would outshine it by at least a thousand times. Are these bodies made up of the same elements as the earth?

This means a Physical Survey of the heavens on a stupendous scale. It was first initiated by Secchi in Italy, but carried out by Lockyer in England, and Pickering in America. At the Harvard College Observatory, the spectra of more than two hundred-thousand stars have been photographed and examined within the last forty years.

The results are, at first sight, rather perplexing for the theories of stellar evolution. By the naked eye, we can distinguish between four classes of stars – bluish white, white, yellow and red. These four classes represent four different stages of evolution, the bluish-white stars being the hottest (temperature $> 15000^{\circ}\text{C}$), the red stars being the coldest (temperature $> 5000^{\circ}\text{C}$). It was believed by most astronomers that the nebulae, by a process of gradual condensation, evolved into white stars. These, cooling with age, passed through the yellow red and deer red stages, finally to darkness and extinction, e.g., the moon which represents the lowest rung of the process.

But the spectra were rather perplexing. The whitest stars showed only lines of the lightest of elements, hydrogen and helium. These gradually grow fainter, and are replaced by a number of metallic lines, which are produced in the laboratory under a great stimulus. At the lowest stages even these tend to disappear, and a set of lines, produced in the laboratory under a low stimulus, come out.

But how are the spectra to be explained? We can detect sodium in the earth, in the sun, in a still hotter star, but not in the white stars. If the stars are composed of the same material, the ninety-two elements which are present in the earth ought to be present in the sun, and in the stars. But as a matter of fact, we obtain only hydrogen and helium in the stars which are in the first stage of evolution. Where are the other elements?

The answer was attempted by Lockyer in his famous "Inorganic Evolution". It was like Icarus's flight, unsuccessful in its ultimate aim, but bringing to light a copious harvest of facts which served as the basis of further work. Lockyer pictured to himself that all elements are products of evolution of simpler constituents, of which hydrogen and helium, and one hypothetical nebularium are probably the chief. The elements are a sort of compound of these primordial elements. Metallic elements disappear in the higher stars, because under the high temperature prevailing there, they are broken up into simpler constituents, or into a proto form. With the aging of the star in course of time, elements known in the earth are formed, or evolved. The whole scientific world was then under the spell of Darwin's idea of evolution, and people smell evolution everywhere.

But Lockyer failed to support his views by experimental proof. Thousands were the experiments which he performed for breaking up the atom and getting hydrogen or helium out of them, but not one was successful. Moreover in those days, the physicists' vision was limited by the idea of the inviolability of the atom and Lockyer's views were regarded in orthodox scientific quarters as a sort of scientific heresy. But this idea of the indivisibility of the atom has now followed many other scientific dogmas into oblivion. In 1897, Thompson split up the atom, and discovered a more minute constituent, the electron, the atom of negative electricity, whose weight is two thousand times less than that of the hydrogen atom. Recently Rutherford, has shown that the atom is a very complicated compound of the two prime elements, the electron, and the proton. The proton is the atom of positive electricity, the amount of electricity on it being the same as the amount on the electron, but it has the same weight as the atom of hydrogen. Hydrogen is the simplest compound we have of these two primordial elements. The other elements are somewhat complicated compounds. In all elements, the positive electricity is concentrated at the centre, the electrons rotate round it in paths of various shapes. When these paths are

disturbed, light is produced. Under some circumstances, the outer electron may get detached from the atom, as for example when the atom is hit by a rapidly moving electron, or a light-pulse, or by another atom. In the atom, now, the positive charge exceeds the negative charge by one unit, in technical language, it is said to be "ionised". The process is known as "ionisation". The properties of these ionised atoms are entirely distinct from those of the ordinary atom.

The electrical theory of matter has ushered a new era into the history of science, and already innumerable applications have been made of it. "In astrophysics, the application which bids fair to open up a field of very great importance was first made, a year or so ago, by Dr. Meghnad Saha, an East Indian, who is a professor in the University of Calcutta." (*Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific, December, 1920, p. 280.*)

Thus says Dr. H. N. Russell professor of Astronomy in the Princeton University, New Jersey, U.S.A., who was awarded the gold medal of the Royal Astronomical Society of Great Britain for his contributions to the theory of Stellar Evolution in 1919. Professor Russell, like many other astronomers, pondered for many years why certain types of stars are seemingly composed of only a few select elements? Why in the sun only 45 elements are found instead of the 92 elements known on the earth?

The answer given by Saha is as follows : – In the sun and the stars physical conditions are entirely determined by the temperature. So we have to trace out what happens to matter, if it is heated from the lowest temperatures to, say, 20000°C. The effect of an increasing high temperature is increased division. Solids become liquid, liquids become vapours. The vapours which consist of the gaseous molecules, may be either simple or compound. In case they are compound, further heating will decompose them into elementary gases, which consist of discreet atoms. There the physicist of the old school came to a halt. But what happens next?

In the next stage, atoms begin to be decomposed into their elements, electrons and protons. The step is not sudden, but gradual. At first, the atom begins to swell, which becomes manifest from the fact that the atom, which was dark before, now becomes luminous. At various stages of swelling, different sets of spectral lines are emitted. A further heating results in the loss of one of the outermost electrons. The atom is then said to be ionised. Further heating results in the

swelling of the ionised atom, which is indicated by the emission of another set of spectral lines which are found in very hot stars.

All these steps were not only mapped out, but calculated in approximate terms by Saha. The great German physical chemist, Nernst, who won the Nobel Prize in Chemistry in 1921, has given us a formula by means of which the decomposition of a compound into elements can be calculated from other physical data. Saha showed that with certain additions and alterations the same equation gives us a formula for calculating the ionisation and radiation of gases. (*Observatory, September, 1920*) .

In the calculation of the process of ionisation, the first thing to be known is the amount of force (or rather work) which is required to tear off the electrons from the atomic system. This is different in different atoms. As a rule, in the atoms which are chemically very active, electrons are very easily torn off. In the atoms which are inert, the electron is bound to the atom with great force. Two atoms of hydrogen, when they combine with each other yield a molecule, and about 80000 calories of heat are evolved in the formation of 6×10^2 of such molecules. Similarly there is a heat of ionisation evolved, when the electron combines with the ionised atom. This heat of ionisation need not be directly determined, but can be obtained from electrical experiments. It gives a direct measure of the force with which the electron is bound to the atom.

How these ideas have helped to clear the problems of the sun will be clear from the following quotations from Dr. Russell's paper.

"Take now an element easy to ionize, like sodium. On the Sun's surface at 6000°, calculation shows that the internal disturbance of the atoms will be so great that most of them will be ionized. In the spots, the proportion will be smaller. Now the neutral sodium atom alone can give the familiar spectral lines of sodium – the ionized atoms giving lines in the far ultraviolet. However, in the spots, where the proportion of sodium atoms which are not ionized must be greater, the sodium lines should be stronger, and so they are, all of them."

"Potassium, which is easier to ionize, shows the same effect to a more marked extent. The rare alkali metal rubidium is still easier to ionize. Its lines do not appear in the solar spectrum at all. This suggests that in the solar atmosphere it

is completely ionized, leaving practically no atoms in a condition to absorb the lines that we are looking for, but that in the spots there may be enough of the neutral atoms to produce the lines. *This was predicted by Saha*, and when I went to Mount Wilson I looked the lines up on some beautiful photographs which had been made by Mr. Brackett – and found the lines in the spot spectrum just as had been predicted, thereby adding a new element to the rest of those known to be present white stars, even at the surface, are much hotter than the Sun. At such high temperatures the metallic vapours must be completely ionized, so that, there are no neutral atoms left to absorb the arc lines, while most of their atoms have lost electrons, and are no longer in a position to give even the enhanced lines. The permanent gases, however, are much harder to ionize, and their atoms are therefore in the singly ionized or neutral states, so that they may be recognized in the spectrum—oxygen and nitrogen by their enhanced lines, and helium, which has the highest known ionization potential, by the lines of the neutral atom. At the relatively low temperature of the Sun, the excitation is not great enough to stimulate absorption of the subordinate series of helium (which alone lie in the visible spectrum) and is barely sufficient to do so for oxygen; while hydrogen, which is easier to ionize, gives strong lines. Such considerations not only explain these apparent difficulties, they open up a new way of determining the surface-temperatures of the stars, which Saha has already used effectively;" (*Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific, December, 1920.*)

A word or two of explanation is probably necessary. Most of the readers have probably heard of sun-spots. They are round black spots which burst forth from time to time in the body of the sun. It is supposed that they are a sort of vortical disturbance in the sun, attended with a great lowering of temperature, say to 4000° from 6000°C. Dr. Saha calculates from his equations that Rubidium and Caesium, on account of their small heat of ionisation, are completely broken up in the sun, but in the spot, the broken parts will reunite, and rubidium will occur in the neutral form. This prediction was verified by Dr. Russell.

In the solar body, sometimes brilliant white patches, known as faculae, are seen. They are the opposite of spots, namely, regions having a higher temperature than the average body of the sun. Saha predicted that these regions would show increased ionisation. This prediction has been verified by Prof. Ch. St. John of the California University.

"Saha has adopted the Nernst equation for the equilibrium of gases reaction to the determination of the percentage of ionized to unionized atoms as a function of temperature and pressure. The Saha equation suggests, as he points out, that in the spectrum of faculae, owing to their higher temperature, the percentage of ionization should be increased, and the enhanced lines strengthened. Preliminary spectrograms of faculae show changes in the intensity of enhanced lines in agreement with this deduction, in direction of higher temperature." (*Physical Review, April, 1922.*)

The Saha-theory signifies much more than mere detection of missing elements, or accounting for their absence from the stellar worlds. Applied to the stars, it has explained their spectra very satisfactorily and has again set the evolution theory on its legs. It has done much more than that, Light is the only messenger between ourselves and the worlds in Space. The spectral lines tell much more than merely indicating the presence of a certain element in the stars. They give us information about the details of physical conditions in these worlds.

The stars may not exert any influence on us, but even the most confirmed utilitarian cannot deny that the sun is the supreme arbiter of the physical conditions in the earth, Even in that early dawn of intellectual life, the Vedic sages worshipped the sun God in the famous hymn, the Gayatri – "Hail to thee, thou great progenitor of the world, thou who quickenest our intellect."

In modern times, the Vedic sage's enthusiasm for the cult of Sun-worship has been succeeded by the knowledge that the Sun is not only the source of all energy and life, but it controls weather and climate – a knowledge of which in advance would be a great boon to mankind. It is now clearly established that when the sun is very active, the magnetic instruments on the earth are disturbed, and there is a great display of 'auroral' light round the poles. Possibly the temperature of the earth as a whole undergoes a change. So a theory which throws light on the physical conditions in the sun cannot but be of great service to mankind.

In America, through the liberality of the late Mr. Carnegie, all observatory has been built on Mount Wilson, at a height of 7000 ft. above the sealevel, for studying the sun, and the stars. This observatory contains the biggest telescope in the earth (100 inch diameter) and probably the best collection of instruments in the world. A devoted band of workers, prob-

ably the brainiest in America, is here continuously at work. The Director, Prof. George Emery Hale, famous in the scientific world for his discovery of magnetic field in sunspots, and who was entrusted during the war with the organisation of America's scientific resources, thus says of the young Indian's contribution to solar physics. The references here allude to Saha's theory of Selective Radiation Pressure, which is distinct from but allied to the ionisation theory.

"Turning to other aspects of the year's work, we may first mention those which bear directly upon this closer alliance with physics and chemistry. For many years certain peculiarities of solar and stellar spectra have baffled all attempts at solution. As an example, it has been impossible to understand why the H and K lines, which certainly belong to calcium, an element of comparatively high atomic weight, nevertheless extend to the highest levels in the solar atmosphere, far outreaching the lines of sodium, magnesium, and other lighter elements, Dr. Megh Nad Saha, Assistant Professor of Physics in the University of Calcutta, has recently offered an explanation which appears to be generally applicable to the interpretation of many of the most puzzling phenomena of solar and stellar spectra. According to this view, the H and K lines are the enhanced lines of a calcium atom which has lost one electron, whereas the fundamental line of neutral calcium is 4227. In the higher levels of the chromosphere, where the ionization, which is only partial at the higher pressures of lower levels, becomes complete, neutral calcium and the 4227 line disappear, while H and K, representing the ionized atoms, remain as conspicuous lines. The D-lines of sodium and the b-lines of magnesium are due to the neutral atoms, which are not present at high levels, and the lines corresponding to the ionized atoms of these and other elements fail to appear because they lie in the extreme ultra-violet, with the possible exception of 4481 of magnesium. Space is lacking to give further details, *but Saha has already pointed out many possible applications of his theory, and others will rapidly develop.* In evidence of this, attention is called to the important results obtained by Dr. Henry Norris Russell, Research Associate of the Observatory, who has extended the theory to the case where atoms of several kinds are present, and tested it in a preliminary study of the spectra of sun-spots. Among the interesting results of this work is the discovery in the Sun of rubidium, shown by the presence in the spot spectrum of two lines in the infrared, as predicted by Saha. *A general attack on solar, stellar, and laboratory*

spectra from this point of view, in which. Dr. Russell and other members of the staff will take part, is being organized. In this connection it is expected that the determination of certain ionizing potentials and the study of many other fundamental aspects of the question will be undertaken at the California Institute." (*Astronomical Society of the Pacific, December, 1921, page 298.*)

In the Paris museum of arts, there is a medal illustrating in a beautiful manner the invigorating influence of one science upon another. A lady is sinking with torpor and exhaustion. Another lady comes up and plants a torch in her hand. In the next scene, the lady who was sinking stands up with a new life and fresh vigour.

In the history of the sciences, we often come across dull epochs – when it seems that there is nothing else to be done except in extending the works initiated by former masters; in the pursuit of a particular branch of science, the investigator no longer experiences that pleasing sensation of thrill and expectancy, and scientific work is reduced to the level of mere dry, routine business. Oftentimes, during such dull periods, unexpected light is thrown from a cognate science which instils a new life into it.

Probably no other science furnishes better examples of this type than Astronomy. It has often been called the mother of sciences, for it dates from the very dawn of intellectual life in this earth of ours. Mathematical and physical sciences largely grew up as hand-maids to astronomy. But repeatedly, in course of its progress, it has sunk to the level of a dry routine subject, but it has as often been rescued from that position by borrowing new light from sciences that sprang from it, from mathematics and physics.

In the foregoing pages, we have related how atomic physics came to the aid of astronomy and it is a matter of gratification to us that this happy union was effected through the intermediary of an Indian.

"It is a significant pioneering work in a virgin soil..... and is to be greeted as a very important step in the working together of physics and astrophysics" so says Prof. W. Westphal of the Berlin University in presenting a report of the work to the Berlin physical colloquium [*Naturwissenschaft, October, 1921*].

One distinguishing feature of Dr. Saha's work is that it not only closes a period of controversy and doubt, but opens up a new field of research work. Already important applica-

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tions of the ionisation theory have been made by Prof. H. N. Russell and Prof. A. S. King, and more is coming forth in course of time. Prof. Russell says at the conclusion of one of his papers:

“The principles of the ionization theory will evidently be of great importance throughout the whole field of astrophysics. And Dr. Saha has made an application of the highest interest to the question of the physical meaning of stellar spectra. The possibilities of the new method appear to be very great to utilize it fully, years of work will be required to study the behaviour of the elements mentioned above and of others, in the stars, in laboratory spectra and by the direct

measurement of ionization, but the prospect of increase of our knowledge, both of atoms and of stars, as a result of such researches, makes it urgently desirable that they should be carried out.” (*The Astrophysical Journal, March, 1922.*)

Scientific work may be likened, in some respects, to prospecting for gold. Sometimes the gold hunters may be labouring through miles of quartz-veins, without coming across a single pennyweight of gold. At other times, after two or three strokes, he may come across solid nuggets of gold. My young friend, in his search for truth and knowledge, has come across what promises to be a bed of solid nuggets.

